

CURRICULUM DEVELOPMENT FOR MANAGEMENT OF IMMERSIVE TECHNOLOGIES BY PROFESSIONALS IN CULTURAL AND CREATIVE SECTOR

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Introduction

This curriculum was developed under the Erasmus+ project IMMER-CV to equip cultural and creative, current and future professionals with the skills to understand, integrate, and lead immersive technology projects in their sector.

Grounded in the principles of vocational relevance, stakeholder co-creation, and flexible learning pathways, the curriculum reflects the findings of targeted interviews, competence mapping surveys, and participatory workshops held in Athens and Spain. Each module has been shaped to address real training gaps identified by professionals and learners — combining technical know-how, creative fluency, and transversal skills.

The IMMER-CV curriculum is designed to be a flexible tool for upskilling professionals, supporting innovation and technological transition and strengthening capacity across the the evolving CCS landscape.

Objectives

- To equip **professionals, students, and educators in the Cultural and Creative Sector** with the technical, creative, and managerial skills needed to apply immersive technologies effectively in their work, practice, or teaching.
- To **promote interdisciplinary collaboration** by bridging the gap between technology, art, and cultural practice.
- To **support the digital transition of the CCS** by addressing real skill requirements identified through stakeholder engagement.
- To offer a **modular training framework** that can be implemented in diverse educational and professional contexts with emphasis on real hands-on experience.
- To promote **lifelong learning and inclusive education** by empowering diverse learners including unprivileged societal groups to co-create immersive experiences.

Target Groups

Early-career professionals

Educators and Trainers

Graduates & Marginalised Learners

Cultural & creative practitioners

Job Seekers

Curriculum Overview

The IMMER-CV curriculum is a modular and interdisciplinary training programme designed to build the capacity of professionals, students, and educators in the Cultural and Creative Sectors (CCS) to effectively engage with immersive technologies. Each module blends technical knowledge, creative design, and transversal skills, offering a balanced, practice-oriented learning experience.

Key features:

- **Duration:** 2.5 months Full-time or 5 months part-time training
- **Format:** Hybrid
- **Approach:** Learner-centered and project-based, grounded in real CCS use cases and sector needs
- **Structure:** Modules supported with learning objectives, competences, and delivery methods
- **Suitability:** Designed for flexible use across vocational training institutions, universities, cultural organisations, and educational programmes
- **Implementation Requirements:**
 - Personnel with relevant expertise in all domains of the curriculum
 - Access to equipment and facilities for hands-on training (e.g. VR/AR headsets,)
 - Institutional Support: Recognised training or cultural institution capable of certifying learners
 - External Collaboration (At least 1 Institute): To enable real-world project implementation and institutional partnership.

Participant Profile & Access Requirements

Educational Background:

- Suitable for learners with post-secondary education or equivalent professional experience in the Cultural and Creative Sectors (CCS), digital media, or related fields.

Foundational Skills:

- Participants should have basic digital literacy and a general understanding of the cultural and/or technological landscape. Module 1 is designed to level the field for those entering from diverse disciplines.

Inclusion Strategy:

- The curriculum promotes inclusion by offering a modular and adaptable structure that can be tailored to diverse learner needs, including linguistic, cultural, or educational differences. Institutions are encouraged to adjust delivery to support equitable participation.

Supportive Entry Pathways:

- Orientation materials and Module 1 are expected to assist diverse learners in onboarding, while peer-to-peer support mechanisms are highly recommended to foster collaboration and help bridge the trainees' diverse educational and cultural backgrounds.

IMMER-CV Curriculum

Module Title	Contact Hours Duration(hrs)	ECVET	EQF	Brief Objective
1. Fundamentals of Immersive Technologies and Job Market Needs	15	1	4	Overview of emerging immersive technologies, key CCS applications, and current job market demands.
2. Technical Foundations of Immersive Production	40	5	5	Gain practical skills in software, hardware, and systems integration.
3. Creative Design and Immersive Aesthetics	40	5	5	Develop creative concepts and aesthetics for immersive media.
4. Tools and Workflow for Immersive Production	30	4	5	Manage tools, UX, and project workflows in immersive production.
5. Personal and Interpersonal Skills for interdisciplinary Teams	25	1	4	Build soft skills for collaboration, leadership, and problem-solving.
6. Hands-On Lab / Individual Immersive Project	70	6	5	Apply skills to develop and present an immersive project prototype.

Module 1

Fundamentals of Immersive Technologies and Job Market Needs

C. H. Duration *	15 hours	ECVET	1	EQF Level	4
Learning Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Understand immersive technologic tools and approaches• Explore immersive tech applications in the CCS sector• Recognize key job roles and professions• Understand current market trends and skill demands				
Lectures	1. Understanding Immersive Technologies				
	Type	Lecture		C. H. Duration	10 hours
	2. Immersive Applications in CCS			*C. H. Duration stands for Contact Hours Duration	
	Type	Lecture		C. H. Duration	2 hours
Lectures	3. Professions and Trends in the Immersive Field				
	Type	Structured Workshop + Formative Assessment		C. H. Duration	3 hours
Learning Outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Core tech definitions and tools' types, uses and capabilities of immersive technologies, historical evolution of immersive media and theoretical frameworks• Real-world CCS use cases (museums, heritage, arts, etc.)• Identification of relevant roles and competencies, Analysis on how trends affect job opportunities				

Module 2

Technical Foundations of Immersive Production (1/2)

C.H. Duration	40 hours	ECVET	5	EQF Level	5
Learning Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none">Learn core functionalities of immersive development tools (e.g. Unity, Unreal Engine)Understand principles of 3D modelling, asset creation and spatial designOperate and configure immersive hardware (headsets, sensors, projection systems)Integrate software and hardware into cohesive immersive prototypes for practical use.				
Lectures	1. Exploring Core Tools for Immersive Production				
	Type	Lecture + Live Demonstration		C. H. Duration	6 hours
	2. 3D Modelling and Asset Preparation (2 rounds)				
	Type	Lecture + Experimentation Rooms		C. H. Duration	6 hours
	3. Setting Up and Operating Immersive Hardware				
	Type	Workshop		C. H. Duration	8 hours

Module 2

Technical Foundations of Immersive Production (2/2)

Lectures	4. Integrating Systems (Software & Hardware) for Immersive Experiences			
	Type	Collaborative Group Task	C. H. Duration	10 hours
Lectures	5. Prototype Setup			
	Type	Gamification	C. H. Duration	10 hours
Learning Outcome	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Use 3D modeling, rendering, and real-time engines (like Unity / Unreal Engine basics)• Create and adapt basic 3D assets for immersive experiences (like Blender, Cinema 4D, Maya)• Set up and troubleshoot immersive hardware installations (trackers, displays, sensors).• Integrate software and hardware into a testable prototype to validate processes like calibration, mapping and system• Present and explain a simple technical setup for immersive use			

Module 3

Creative Design & Storytelling for Immersive experiences (1/2)

C. H. Duration	40 hours	ECVET	5	EQF Level	5
Learning Objective	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Understand storytelling principles and narrative structures in immersive experiences• Explore visual, spatial, and sensory design in immersive environments• Apply design thinking for audience-centered concept development• Develop creative proposals tailored to CCS applications				
Lectures	1. Narrative Design in Immersive Experiences				
	Type	Lecture + Collaborative Group Task		C. H. Duration	6 hours
	2. Aesthetic and Sensory Composition				
	Type	Lecture + Experimentation Rooms		C. H. Duration	10 hours
Lectures	3. Creative Ideation and Co-Creation				
	Type	Structured co-creation Workshop		C. H. Duration	8 hours

Module 3

Creative Design & Storytelling for Immersive experiences (2/2)

Lectures	4. Design Thinking for Cultural Experiences and Psychology of Immersive Perception			
	Type	Lecture + Collaborative Group Task	C. H. Duration	8 hours
Learning Outcomes	5. Concept Pitch and Peer Feedback			
	Type	Learner Presentation + Gamification + Formative Assessment	C. H. Duration	8 hours
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Apply visual storytelling techniques to immersive experience design• Create immersive storyboards and user-centered experience concepts• Use multisensory and spatial design strategies• Tailor immersive concepts to different CCS contexts and audiences using ideation tools (mind maps, personas)• Present and refine a creative idea based on peer and trainer feedback				

Module 4

Tools and Workflow for Immersive Production (1/2)

C. H. Duration	30 hours	ECVET	4	EQF Level	5
Learning Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Understand the stages, roles, and tools involved in immersive production in the CCS• Apply basic project management and team coordination techniques tailored to immersive media workflows• Integrate UX principles and interdisciplinary collaboration into the production process• Recognise key financial elements of immersive projects, including budgeting, resource planning, and bus. models				
Lectures	1. Production Workflows, Team Roles and Budgeting				
	Type	Lecture + Individual Exercise	C. H. Duration	6 hours	
	2. Project Management and Business Models for Immersive Projects				
	Type	Lecture + Individual exercise (based on a real case study)	C. H. Duration	6 hours	
Lectures	3. UX and User-Centered Design in Immersive Environments				
	Type	Experimentation Rooms + Collaborative Group Task	C. H. Duration	8 hours	

Module 4

Tools and Workflow for Immersive Production (2/2)

4. Audience Development, Outreach, External Collaborations and Workflow Simulation

Type

Collaborative Group Task + Learner Presentation +
Formative Assessment

C. H. Duration

8 hours

Lectures

5. Ethical, Regulatory, and Inclusion Guidelines

Type

Lecture

C. H. Duration

2 hours

Learning
Outcomes

- Apply basic project management methods using Agile and waterfall methods and planning tools (e.g., Gantt charts, Trello, Miro) to coordinate interdisciplinary teams, immersive project delivery, project planning and task allocation
- Incorporate UX research methods (e.g., journey mapping, feedback loops) into imm. experience design processes.
- Understanding of core financial and strategic components of immersive media projects, including budgeting, business models, stakeholder engagement and outreach, strategic collaborations and market awareness.
- Recognise ethical, regulatory, and inclusion-related considerations in immersive content creation, ensuring responsible design and broader audience accessibility.

Module 5

Personal and Interpersonal Skills for Interdisciplinary Teams

C. H. Duration	25 hours	ECVET	1	EQF Level	4
Learning Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Strengthen collaboration and communication in multidisciplinary teams• Develop leadership, adaptability, and conflict resolution skills• Apply reflective thinking and feedback techniques in creative settings				
Lectures	1. Effective Communication in Immersive Teams				
	Type	Lecture + Collaborative Group Task		C. H. Duration	15 hours
	2. Decision-Making in Creative Projects, Problem Solving and Conflict Resolution				
	Type	Lecture + Structured Co-Creation Workshop		C. H. Duration	10 hours
Learning Outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Techniques to communicate effectively in interdisciplinary teams• Apply teamwork and basic leadership strategies in creative environments• Respond constructively to team challenges and project feedback				

Module 6

Hands-On Lab / Individual Immersive Project

C. H. Duration	70 hours	ECVET	6	EQF Level	5
Learning Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create and present a functional immersive project prototype. & Evaluate and select projects through peer review. • Implement selected projects in collaboration with cultural institutions, managing planning, budgeting, audience interaction, and real-world testing. 				
Lectures	1. Immersive Project – Development Phase				
	Type	Individual Exercise or Collaborative Group Task + Access to Tools/Facilities + Mentoring Sessions		C. H. Duration	25 hours
Lectures	2. Immersive Project – Presentation & Evaluation				
	Type	Learner Presentation / Project Pitch + Competition and/or Hackathon + Collective voting process to select project(s) to be implemented in real-world conditions in Lecture 3		C. H. Duration	5 hours
Lectures	3. From Prototype to Practice: Real Installations in Museums or Cultural Venues				
	Type	On-site Real-World Implementation + Institutional Collaboration + Evaluation Based on Public Engagement and Exhibition Outcomes		C. H. Duration	40 hours
Learning Outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop and showcase an immersive experience based on real-world criteria and user feedback. • Collaborate with cultural institutions to deliver, test, and assess the impact of implemented projects. 				

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